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Categorizing student's learning strategy as a basis to improve their educational results.

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ABSTRACT

Companies desire for well-educated engineers because they want to optimize the company's processes and invest in technical developments. It is therefore seen as an assignment for Universities to achieve a high efficiency in educating many engineers for these companies. This means that Universities need to attract students and to make sure that the number of dropouts in the first year is minimal. In practice we see the opposite happening. Already in the first semester, students' motivation seems to decrease dramatically and even quite an amount of students leave the University. This amount needs to be decreased as much as possible. Motivation is related to the learning strategies students use in practice. A tool is developed which enables study Counsellors to measure, to a certain extent, what the learning strategy is of a student and how, if it would be disadvantageous, an unfortunate situation can be changed. Using the tool in practice shows that it would help to lower the dropout rate. The first results seem to be positive. In the coming academic year this tool will be used to a full extent.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Curriculum Development, and Attractiveness of Engineering Education.

Keywords: Motivation, first year students, learning strategies, improving methodology

INTRODUCTION

Now, leaving behind the financial crisis, markets again are flourishing. Companies regain markets and are increasingly selling their goods. These companies are investing in innovation of their products, and engineers taking a significant part in the researches to find and realize innovative products, which necessarily need to be sold on those markets. It's seen that on one hand companies desperately are seeking more young engineers to start their career in their companies but on the other hand Universities of engineering need to provide these companies with well-educated starting engineers. Therefore, it is important that Universities of engineering attract many starting students. But often it is the perception of these youngsters that the engineering education is too difficult, using 'complex' mathematics and physics. That could be the cause of many youngsters not to choose for an engineering education. Students, who are starting at the University, encounter most likely a different approach of learning compared to the learning approaches they were accustomed with in their former high schools. In Universities, students themselves need to be

responsible for their learning behaviour. It also often occurs that the real educational situations in University do not meet their expectations and perceptions. It is additionally seen that students, nowadays, use their mobile phone in class very often and in some cases students even have a form of game addiction, which makes them having less time for school businesses or even see they need to work during school hours for living. On the other hand, there is a tough scheme of learning activities and they have to come up with positive exam results and tasks relatively fast. As a consequence of some or all of these occurring situations, students develop lack of motivation and, in worst case; they drop out of the University. In [1], [2] and [3], clues for this lack of motivation has already been seen. They also pose some clues for a starting development a lack of motivation in the definition of the four stages of learning strategies of Maslow, especially in the first stage. Students probably enter the University with having an 'unconsciously incompetent' attitude in their approach mastering the engineering content of the lectures and other educational programmes. It can be observed these students are frequently making wrong choices in operating their learning styles and controlling their educational programme satisfactorily. To help students in their struggle for mastering the engineering curriculum and becoming good professional engineers, it is important that Universities try to understand what effects their motivation and correspondingly to this, what effects their learning strategies, after which University can help students to regain motivation and have a progressive result in their continuing engineering education.

In 2015, a first paper was presented at the SEFI Conference in Orleans about a research carried out by [Name University], Mechanical Engineering, on what causes to block student's motivation to continue their engineering education. In the research, it became clear that great numbers of students show their lack of motivation already after the first few weeks of their education. However, the research was not based on finding elements of intrinsic or extrinsic taxonomy of student's motivation. The purpose of that research was to gain insight into students' learning strategies in a relatively simple way. From this information it is aimed for to find ways and methods to improve motivation, to ensure that students stay in University and to increase the effectiveness of their work. In [4] an overview study of learning strategies, as it was researched in engineering education, can be found.

The [Name University] approach can be found in the SEFI 2015 paper [5]. A questionnaire was used to ask students about the level they want to reach in terms of a grade, next to the question on how much effort they want to put into their education, in order to reach that grade. From that information 6 categories of learning strategies were distinguished. Where [5] is showing a measurement set up of motivation as it was used in 2015, in this paper the next step is presented. At [Name University] Engineering, Study Counsellor check and help students with their study results. These Study Counsellor are very essential in contact with the students. In their discussions with their students, they are provided with information on motivation of these students. These Study Counsellor than can have discussions with the separate groups of students having the same kind of lack of motivation. They can discuss what is the reason for their lack of motivation and what can be done to regain student's motivation. These counsellors can discuss improvement of students' learning strategies. The [Name University] University wants to get more insights into using this tool and to understand better what is happening during the first semester to a student's motivation. The goal is to take action and to ensure student's motivation does not eventually result into such dramatically dropout rates. In the paper a

conclusion of this research will be drawn, and especially what were the experiences of the Study Counsellor?

1 FINDING STUDENT'S LEARNING STRATEGIES

In our research we see possibilities to measure students' motivation and connect this to their learning strategies in a relatively easy way. In this paper it is the focus how the information coming from the questionnaires can be transformed to advices towards students on how to improve their learning strategies. From the information from the questionnaires, it is supposed students' motivation can be perceived. The students answered the questionnaires in November 2016 and in March 2017. Some questions are included, where students can indicate to what level their motivation is. Also two indirect questions on motivation were asked. 1: What is your commitment to reach for a grade, and 2: How long would you do homework in order to get this grade? In the Netherlands, grades are given in a score from 1 to 10. 5.5 is just a positive grade and lower than that is a negative grade. For the grades 4 levels is used.

- 1 Just sufficient: students don't have intention to reach more than (5,5-6).
- 2 Normal grade: this is normally what students will reach (6-7).
- 3 Higher grade: students really want to achieve higher grade (7-8).
- 4 Excellent grade: students want to be excellent (8-9).

For the amount of work on doing homework, six stages are defined. The stages are divided from hardly any commitment to do homework (a few minutes of doing homework per day), till having a challenging commitment (more than one and half hours of doing homework per day). In the next enumeration the six stages of doing homework is listed up.

- 1 $0 < h < 0.2$ hours/day: No work commitment (<1 hours/week)
- 2 $0.2 < h < 0.4$ h/d: too little work commitment (1-2 h/w)
- 3 $0.4 < h < 0.8$ h/d: work commitment for possible positive results (2-4 h/w)
- 4 $0.8 < h < 1.2$ h/d: more than normal commitment (4-6 h/w)
- 5 $1.2 < h < 1.6$ h/d: hard working commitment (6-8 h/w)
- 6 $h > 1.6$ h/d: Extensive work commitment (>8 h/w)

With these two data combined in a two-dimensional graph, an estimation of categories on learning strategies of the students can be acquired. In the two-dimensional graph below, Figure 1, zones of certain learning strategies are shown. When students showing their commitment to what level of grade they want to reach in combination to the amount of hours of homework they want to spend to get this grade is seen as combined information to which a classification of learning strategies can be identified. This learning strategy of the student is the basis where personal study coaches can have discussion on in order to help this student making decisions accepting a more effective learning strategy and gather a better result for the upcoming education.

Fig. 1. Attempt to classify levels of learning strategies

In Figure 1 six different students' learning strategies were distinct:

1. **Demanding strategy:** students want to work very hard in order to achieve the highest grades possible. Often these students can easily have good results in their education and want to do special work, e.g. doing an honours programme.
2. **Want-to-win strategy:** students estimate that spending the maximum amount of time on homework will enable them to have average/sufficient marks. These students see they need to work hard to get higher grades and they are very motivated to do extra work to get normal grades.
3. **Survival strategy:** students think they need to work hard for getting an engineering degree. They believe or feel they have not the right cognitive capabilities to get normal grades, so they are willing to work very hard to achieve this goal.
4. **Nominal strategy:** students' intent to achieve good marks by working a nominal amount of time on homework. These students are seen as students achieving nominal educational results by working a nominal time on their homework.
5. **Not realistic strategy:** students' work under the assumption that they are able to invest a minimum amount of time to no time for their homework and nonetheless getting maximum high marks. But it can also be that these students are brilliant and need to go to the academic University or they have arrogant thinking that the education is too easy for them.
6. **No strategy:** students without specific strategy. It can be the case that these students are struggling for finding out if mechanical engineering is really something for them.

Helping students to change their learning strategies is concerning students selected for the learning strategies: 'Not realistic strategy', 'No strategy' and 'Surviving' Strategy. The approach is to convince students to change their way of learning to the other learning strategies. In Figure 2 the arrows are showing what the intention is of the Study Counsellor. They want to discuss with students on how to change their unfortunate learning strategy into a more successful strategy.

Fig. 2. Change direction of non-effective learning strategies to the more effective

In the methodology composed Study Counsellor are an important element really being able to discuss with students changing their unfortunate learning strategies into more fruitful learning strategies. But how this discussing should take place? Especially for this intervention a questioning and answering table was assembled. In Table 1 in total 13 questions were formulated. Students can answer in a 5-point Likert scale. But it is always the question what are the perceptions of the students answering to the questions. What is their perception to fill in a 3 and is this the same perception for another student? It is likely each student has his own perception about the five levels of answering. In order to harmonize the answering each level of the Likert scale is given a written answer. Students have to choose which of those five answers are the most likely to their situation.

Students can choose the right answer to their situation. Study Counsellor can use, for each student, the outcome of filling in this table as discussion items. To the far right (5) students, to their opinion really function perfectly, while to the far left students really expressing themselves that there is something not okay. Counsellors can use the outcome as a discussion document on which they can consider together with the student what is the best thing to do, and how a student can change from the left side more to the direction of the right side? So the table can be used to give students possibilities to express their motivation and an advice to change their motivation in order to obtain better results in the engineering education. In the next paragraph the outcome of the inquiry will be presented.

Table 1. Answering table formulating student's learning strategy

	QUESTION	ANSWER				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	What do you expect from your education?	I don't see education is helping me realize my career wishes.	I'm struggling if this is what I want, but I want do technical education.	I have difficulties to focus what to become in my career.	I know that engineering is what I want. But I need specialisation focus.	I really can grow. I see what to become. I want to do more.
1 ^a	How does your environment effect your education?	Somehow it was not my decision to come to engineering.	I'm doubtful about right education. My environment isn't supportive.	It was my decision, but I cannot discuss this with my environment.	I see in my environment what is the work of an engineer. I like that.	My parents really are proud about me and my friends too.
2	Do you accept your educational situation?	I can't accept the today's situation. I want to change it.	I want information about going somewhere else.	I doubting if this situation is what I want.	I accept today's situation, but I want to make some changes.	I fully accept my today's situation.
2 ^a	Do you accept the demand of doing homework?	Homework is not what I want. I make no homework.	I can't get the motivation to do homework.	I'm doing just what I think is needed to pass exams.	I see that if I don't make homework I won't pass exams	I'm focussing on higher grades, so I do homework to be able to get those.
2 ^{aa}	Are you aware of the success factors getting positive grads?	I don't know and don't want to know what success criteria are.	I don't know why success criteria will help me.	I want to know what success criteria are.	For some courses I do know but for other I don't know.	I know for every course what the success criteria are.
2 ^{ab}	Are you resilient when things are going wrong?	I see my results are bad but I don't want to do more work.	I thought I couldn't engineering and it seems I was right.	I'm not demotivated, but when things are going wrong it demotivates me.	I see that it is important to do work extra hard, but I have several other things to do.	I can find extra motivation to do things better after they went wrong.
2 ^b	Do you see the demands of doing engineering work?	I don't know what the demands of engineering are. It's about Physics.	I will see what the demands are. Now I'm focussing on my education results.	I'm eager what the demands of engineering are.	I know, in some cases, what the demands of engineering are.	I see what an engineer needs to do. I work already in an engineering company.
2 ^{ba}	Are appealed to the Engineering work?	I think I'm not on the right education.	I doubt if engineering is my education.	I know that the engineering profession is giving me a good career.	Engineering is really what I want, but not in which kind of engineering direction.	Engineering is really what I want. I know what I want to become in this profession.
2 ^{bb}	Do you have perceptions of your future profession?	I don't know if engineering is part of my feel good in the future.	I want to talk to someone who can tell me more about an engineer career.	I need to have more information what a possible engineering task contains.	Engineering is really my career but I don't know in what kind of company.	I already know what I want to reach in the future in an engineering job.
3	What were your grades in preparatory school?	I just passed. For mathematics I had a negative grade	I just passed. For mathematics was just positive.	I passed quite easily. For mathematics I had a high grade.	I had all grades positive, but not very high	I had high grades for every part.
3 ^a	What is your intellectual capability?	I feel I can't understand the engineering knowledge. Especially mathematics.	I think I can get my propaedeutic certificate in two years if I work hard.	I must work hard to get my propaedeutic certificate in 1 year.	My results are good. I'm going to pass in 1 year.	I'm really doing well. My mean grade is > 7.
4	What is your financial situation?	I have to do everything alone. I must work for living.	Sometimes I think what to do about my financial situation.	My financial situation is not hindering me doing the engineering education.	My financial situation is not a problem.	I have no financial problems. My parents helping me.
5	Do you have the will to change your learning strategies when needed?	No, it is taking me too much time.	I want to change only if it is not effecting my daily live.	I don't know. Can I get some help of someone?	If it makes me getting better, I'm certainly willing to change.	My strategy is ok and my results too.

2 DATA

The method proposed in the previous section is used to map the learning strategies and study motivation of Mechanical Engineering students that started their education in the academic year 2016-2017. We asked the students to fill out the questionnaire twice and see whether their learning strategies and study motivation change in time during the year. The first time we questioned them was in November 2016 and the second time in March 2017.

2.1 Results of the questionnaire

The distribution of the students per learning strategy is found in *Table 2*. Between 2016, November and 2017, March already 20 students decided to quit the education (16%). There were only 17 students that participated in both the survey in November 2016 and the one in March 2017. From this subgroup of students, 12 students didn't change the learning strategy during that period. Three of them moved from want-to-win strategy to surviving strategy, one student from demanding strategy to want-to-win strategy and one student from nominal strategy to not-realistic strategy.

Table 2 Information and results of the motivation questionnaire

	2016, November	2017, March
# students	122	102
# respondents	37	66
# no strategy	0	2
# not realistic strategy	0	0
# surviving strategy	7	11
# nominal strategy	9	18
# want-to-win strategy	13	26
# demanding strategy	8	9

After the first semester Study Counsellors give each student a Study Progress Indication (SPI). This indication is practically based on the number of credit point obtained at the moment the SPI is awarded by the study coach. The Study Progress Indication is to be explained as:

- A – On schedule (student progress is up to standard)
- B – Initial signs of study delay
- C – Considerable study delay
- D – Serious study delay

An SPI – D at the end of the first year means that the student has obtained less than 45 credit points out of 60 and therefore, as it is the policy out education, has to quit the educational program. We will use this indicator to validate the information from the Tables 2 and 3.

Table 3 SPI at the moment the third questionnaire is filled out.

	STUDY PROGRESS INDICATION			
	A	B	C	D
# no strategy	0	1	1	0
# not realistic strategy	0	0	0	0
# surviving strategy	1	1	5	4
# nominal strategy	0	6	8	4
# want-to-win strategy	2	8	9	7
# demanding strategy	2	4	2	1

Students with a D indication in March are considerable candidates to leave the education at the end of the year. The majority of these students have a want-to-win strategy, surviving strategy or nominal strategy. This indicates that these students say we want to do our best to achieve positive grades but the reality is otherwise. Study Counsellors can discuss with these students what the reason was for these severe delays in learning results. For these students it is the last call to change. Otherwise they are really not capable to stand the demands of the education.

Another good indicator for the possibility in succeeding the engineering education is the final grade for mathematics in the secondary school, since we see this as a relevant indicator that shows, to some extent, the learning capacity of a student, entering the University education. The students entering our University are coming from the VWO (Secondary school level for academic education), as well from HAVO (Secondary school level for bachelor education) and from a middle technical occupational school. From this last group we don't have information on their final grades on mathematics. In Table 4 those grades are given for the respondents to the survey in March 2017. None of the students got an 8 as a final grade for mathematics in their secondary school.

Table 4 Final grades for mathematics in secondary school per learning strategy.

	FINAL GRADE MATHEMATICS			
	5	6	7	9
# no strategy	0	0	2	0
# not realistic strategy	0	0	0	0
# surviving strategy	3	3	5	0
# nominal strategy	1	5	11	1
# want-to-win strategy	1	13	12	0
# demanding strategy	0	3	6	0

Except for the categorisation in learning strategy, the students also respond on the questionnaire of 13 questions from Table 1. The answers from the respondents in March are graphically represented in Fig. 3.

From Fig. 3 it becomes clear that only incidentally students answer with option one. Option two is more often present as an answer, especially for questions 2, 3^a and 4.

Fig. 3 The distribution of answers options given by the students per question.

The results seen in the Figure 3 show that coaches really can have topics to discuss with students in order to understand the background of their not so successful study results. Especially level of answers 1 and 2 give reasons for Counsellors to have discussion with students. As an example, on question 4 students really see the financial situation as an obstacle to spent their attention to education. Counsellors can than discuss the reason and try to discuss, as an example, to lend more money from government, as in the Netherlands students are given the possibility to loan money from Government under relatively advantageous terms. (Low rate and advantageous pay back condition.)

2.2 Results of a single class

As a test case we take a closer look at a single class of 11 Dutch students Mechanical Engineering. The students have filled out the questionnaire. The classification in learning strategies is graphically represented in Fig. 4. Their answers to the questions are given in Table 5.

The first observation is that incidentally all of these students respond with answer 4 to question 5: each one of them is willing to change the learning strategy if it makes him/her getting better. This definitely could be seen as a positive sign to discuss with these students what the best way is to change their learning strategy.

Fig. 4 Classification of students from the test group in the six possible learning strategy categories, according to Fig 1.

Table 5 Answers to the questions (see Table 1) from the students in the test group.

STUDENT	QUESTION												
	1	1 ^a	2	2 ^a	2 ^{aa}	2 ^{ab}	2 ^b	2 ^{ba}	2 ^{bb}	3	3 ^a	4	5
Student 1	4	5	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	3	3	4	4
Student 2	2	4	3	4	4	2	4	5	2	4	2	3	4
Student 3	4	4	5	4	5	4	3	4	3	4	4	4	4
Student 4	4	5	1	4	4	3	4	5	4	5	2	1	4
Student 5	4	4	4	2	4	3	4	4	4	4	2	2	4
Student 6	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	2	2	3	4
Student 7	3	4	4	5	5	5	3	4	4	4	3	4	4
Student 8	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	2	3	4
Student 9	4	2	4	4	3	4	5	2	2	4	2	5	4
Student 10	4	5	4	3	4	4	5	4	4	2	3	4	4
Student 11	4	5	3	4	5	5	2	4	2	4	2	4	4

2.3 Feedback from the Study Counsellors and students

Based on the student’s study progress and his/her answers to the questionnaire, study development coaches reflect on the results with the individual student in a one-to-one conversation in order to find a way to improve the learning strategy. Study Counsellors put the method into practise. Summarizing the experiences of both the students and the study coaches:

1. The questionnaire provides good input for a conversation and gives clues and directions on how to improve students study results. Best would be to use the method in the first week of the academic year. Halfway the academic year students find it hard to change their direction.
2. Students mention that the survey increases their level of awareness with respect to study motivation. Two aspects have influence on the motivation:
 - a. Although students like the education in Mechanical Engineering, they don't know exactly what it will lead to for their future professional careers. More orientation on career possibilities during the first year would be most welcome. Seeing the purpose of their education would increase the motivation.
 - b. Most courses examine in two or more separate parts. Credit points (ECTS, European Credit Transfer System) will only be awarded when a student passes all separate exams. When a student misses one part or more, then no ECTS will be awarded, although in fact the student might have gained "virtual" credit points for the parts he/she did pass. This also influences the motivation.
3. The classification of students in the six categories of learning strategies, as specified in section 1, agrees with the perception of both the Study Counsellors and the students on how the student performs at the moment. Student said: "I agree to be put in the certain learning strategy".
4. The method also works for discussing and raising awareness with a group of students placed in a same learning strategy at the same time. They inspire each other by explaining how to study.

3 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper is giving information about the procedure at [Name University] University of applied Sciences in [place] on how they approach the effect of the occurring situation of lack of motivation of students during the first year. The information gathered can be seen as positive to the use of the new method on the improvement of learning strategies. The result encourages the staff to continue using this method right from the start when students enter the University. The relatively positive feedback from students as well as from accompanying teacher coaches gives us the power to continue with this learning strategy tool. From the next educational year this tool will be used to all students right from the start when they are entering our education. We feel that this method gives us the opportunity to really improve student's learning strategy and therefore increase students' educational results and therefore also their motivation.

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